

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ENCEPHALITIS WITH PROBABLE ALLERGIC ETIOLOGY FOLLOWING SPINAL ANESTHESIA FOR TORSIONED LEFT OVARIAN CYST – CASE REPORT

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Abstract

Spinal anesthesia is an usual procedure, widely considered safe, neurological complications being rare. Encephalitis following spinal anesthesia is exceptional, and an allergic etiology is seldom reported.

Keywords: spinal anesthesia, allergy

Introduction

Spinal anesthesia (also called subarachnoid block) is a form of regional anesthesia in which a local anesthetic is injected into the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) in the subarachnoid space, usually at the lumbar level (L3–L4 or L4–L5). It produces temporary loss of sensation and motor function in the lower part of the body. Onset is rapid, and the block is dense and reliable.

Spinal anesthesia is commonly used for surgeries involving the lower abdomen, pelvis, perineum, and lower limbs, such as: cesarean section, gynecological and urological surgeries, orthopedic procedures, hernia repairs, hemorrhoidectomy, vascular procedures of the lower limbs. It is often chosen when general anesthesia poses higher risks or a fast, reliable, and cost-effective block is needed.

Spinal anesthesia complications can be divided into immediate, early, and late:

- immediate (during/soon after injection): hypotension & bradycardia (due to sympathetic block); total spinal anesthesia (if drug spreads too high) or high spinal block; nausea/vomiting (secondary to hypotension);
- early (hours to days): post-dural puncture headache; backache, urinary retention; neurological injury or aseptic meningitis (very rare);
- late (days to weeks): infection (meningitis, abscess – very rare with aseptic technique); hematoma (spinal/epidural, especially in anticoagulated patients); persistent neurological deficits (extremely rare).

Spinal anesthesia is a widely used and generally safe regional anesthesia technique. Neurological complications are rare, and encephalitis is an exceptional event. We report the case of a young female patient who developed acute encephalitis, possibly related to an immunological mechanism, following spinal anesthesia during surgery for a torsioned ovarian cyst.

Case report

A 28-year-old previously healthy female, underwent exploratory laparotomy with left anexectomy, for torsioned ovarian cyst, under spinal anesthesia with li-

docaine. Within 24 hours, she developed severe headache, generalized pruritus, rash, and low-grade fever, progressing to confusion and meningeal signs at 48 hours. Brain MRI showed bilateral temporal and insular hyperintensities. Cerebrospinal fluid analysis revealed lymphocytic pleocytosis and elevated protein, while viral PCR was negative. Immunological tests demonstrated eosinophilia, elevated IgE, and a weakly positive lymphocyte transformation test for lidocaine. High-dose intravenous corticosteroids and antihistamines resulted in progressive clinical improvement and full neurological recovery within two weeks.

This case highlights a rare but serious complication of spinal anesthesia. Early recognition of possible allergic encephalitis and prompt corticosteroid therapy are crucial for favorable outcomes.

Briefly presentation

Patient: 28-year-old female, previously healthy, no known drug allergies.

Admission diagnosis: left ovarian torsion due to hemorrhagic cyst.

Surgical procedure: exploratory laparotomy with left anexectomy under spinal anesthesia; no intraoperative incidents.

Spinal anesthesia technique: standard aseptic protocol, with xylene 4% 5 ml (lidocaine hydrochloride 200 mg).

Clinic evolution:

- 24 hours postoperatively: severe, diffuse headache resistant to analgesics; generalized pruritus, transient maculopapular rash; low-grade fever (38–38.5°C);
- 48 hours postoperatively: drowsiness, mild confusion, disorientation; positive meningeal signs, no focal deficits; admitted to ICU for neurological monitoring;

Imaging and lab workup:

Brain MRI third day (fig. 1): hyperintensities in bilateral temporal and insular cortices, non-specific but suggestive of encephalitis; ❏

Lumbar puncture - cerebrospinal fluid: clear, lymphocytic pleocytosis (80 cells/mm³), elevated protein (98 mg/dL), normal glucose;

PCR for viral panel: negative (herpes simplex virus, varicello-zosterian virus, enteroviruses);

Immunological tests: elevated total IgE titer: 210 UI/mL;

Peripheral eosinophilia (800/mm³);

ANA and ENA panel: negative;

In vitro lymphocyte transformation test for lidocaine: weakly positive (delayed-type hypersensitivity);

Treatment and Outcome: high-dose IV corticosteroids - Methylprednisolone 1g/day for 3 days; antihistamines - Cetirizine as H1 blocker; neuroprotective therapy and fluid-electrolyte balance.

Progressive clinical improvement over 7 days.

Full neurological recovery at 2-week follow-up.

Fig. 1 Fluid-Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) axial section showing bilateral hyperintensities in the medial temporal lobes and insular cortices (white arrows), consistent with inflammatory changes suggestive of autoimmune or allergic encephalitis. No enhancement after gadolinium contrast.

Discussion

The reported case highlights a rare but serious complication of spinal anesthesia. Although viral encephalitis was considered, negative PCR and lack of direct infectious markers, combined with allergic signs (rash, pruritus, eosinophilia, elevated IgE titer), supported a possible immune-mediated encephalitic reaction.

Hypersensitivity to local anesthetics, especially of type IV delayed type, has been sparsely reported in the literature. While definitive proof is challenging, the positive response to corticosteroids and exclusion of other causes strengthens the allergic hypothesis.

Conclusion

Spinal anesthesia-related encephalitis may have an immunoallergic basis, even in patients without prior allergy history. Early recognition and corticosteroid therapy may be lifesaving and reduce neurologic sequelae. Allergen identification and avoidance in future procedures is essential for patient safety.

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